

Deliverable D14.4

Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year two Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

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1. Executive Summary

The EOSC-ENTRUST Training package aims to support organisations hosting or developing Trusted Research Environments (TREs) with the knowledge and skills required to participate in a secure, interoperable and federated European network of TREs. Building on the foundations made in year 1, the year 2 version of the Training package focuses on federation readiness, guiding TRE Providers preparing to align with the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Architecture, for which the year 2 version (EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3) is published in parallel with this Training package.

During year 2, the Training package has developed from a descriptive overview of Personas into a more structured role-based curriculum. This curriculum connects the operational realities of existing and emerging TREs with the federated network described in the year 2 Blueprint architecture. It identifies the key functions and skills required for TRE Providers to build, operate and sustain compliant environments and introduces draft training modules aligned with the current Blueprint components, Architecture specifications, Template legal agreements, Operating procedures and Interface definitions.

Through systematic review of earlier EOSC-ENTRUST deliverables and interviews with TRE Providers, the Training package identifies and prioritises training gaps. These include a general lack of structured training and onboarding material for TRE operators, a fragmented understanding of legal frameworks and very limited training on federation services such as authentication, authorisation and auditing (AAAI). As a result, a draft modular online guide has been developed and will serve as a living handbook for TRE Providers to consult on such issues. This guide builds on existing material and will throughout year 3 provide step-by-step guidance for implementing Blueprint components.

To conclude, the year 2 version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package has moved from identifying who needs training to defining what these need to be trained in to achieve the federated network outlined in the Blueprint architecture. This provides a foundation for standardised, reusable training material that may enhance trust, interoperability and sustainability across the future EOSC-ENTRUST federation.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A ‘starter pack’ of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	No
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	Yes
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	Yes
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 3 National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 4 The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	No

3. Methods

3.1 Scope of Deliverable

In the first version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package (EOSC-ENTRUST D13.2), we aimed to get an understanding of the actors, or Personas, who were expected to interact with the EOSC-ENTRUST federated network of TREs in one way or another. We then identified training topics relevant to each Persona and began compiling a list of existing training materials on sensitive data and TREs that could be useful for them.

The final aim of the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package is to create a collection of training materials for building interoperable TRE services. In this second version, we therefore began by narrowing in on the various Personas constituting the TRE Providers and pinpointing which training curriculum they need to enable a smooth journey across the EOSC-ENTRUST network for researchers. However, as the project took shape, we determined it was best to align the functions of TRE providers, in contrast to Personas, for better alignment with other EOSC-ENTRUST work packages and Deliverables.

3.2 Relationships with other WPs and deliverables

This deliverable builds on communication across all EOSC-ENTRUST work packages and is influenced by several previous and parallel deliverables. The training content is primarily shaped by the year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Architecture and Interoperability Format (EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3), which is being developed in parallel with this deliverable. The proposed scope and methodology have been discussed and developed throughout biweekly WP-specific meetings as well as in cross-WP events such as the first Driver Blueprint validation workshop in January, the second requirements and capabilities workshop in May (EOSC-ENTRUST M17) and the second evaluation and adoption workshop in September (EOSC-ENTRUST M18). Training needs have been identified from the Providers' first Blueprint evaluation and adoption report (EOSC-ENTRUST D10.1), the Drivers' first Blueprint validation report (EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1) and the revised Driver requirements for TREs (EOSC-ENTRUST M8) and several one-on-one interviews with WP11 Providers. The material in this Training package is further complemented by related efforts in WP17 Technologies and WP20 Workflows.

3.3 Methodology

The year two of the EOSC-ENTRUST training package was developed through a series of meetings and workshops, one-on-one interviews and a thorough revision and cross-mapping of earlier deliverables to update and connect Personas and training needs. The draft training modules were developed by combining existing training and onboarding material targeting TRE Provider staff and mapping these to the user- and operator journeys and federation interfaces simultaneously being developed in the year two version of the Blueprint Architecture.

4. Description of work accomplished

During year two of the EOSC-ENTRUST project, we have focused on gathering concrete evidence on current training practices and gaps across TRE Providers. We have received input from internal EOSC-ENTRUST deliverables and direct interviews with existing and emerging TRE Providers. The goal was to consolidate these insights into a coherent, role-based training curriculum aligned with the year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture.

4.1 Refining EOSC-ENTRUST Personas and roles

Building on the year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST Training package (EOSC-ENTRUST D13.2), we took a stepwise approach to updating and harmonising Personas and roles to ensure consistency. We have received input from the Driver projects, TRE Providers, and relevant frameworks:

EHDS, GDPR and SATRE. Through this, we modified existing roles, expanding them as necessary, as well as identified additional roles that will likely interact with the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. During this process, we realised that although Personas proved valuable in the first iteration, the addition of roles made continuing with this approach cumbersome and at times confusing. In that way, we decided not to develop the Personas further, but rather focus on roles and functions that need to be filled and accomplished, aligned with the user journey described by the Driver forum (EOSC-ENTRUST M8) and the year 2 Blueprint in progress (EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3). We kept the roles and listed potential training needs identified during the interviews and review of frameworks. These roles and training needs are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Revised list of roles and training needs

Updated role	Training needs
TRE/SPE owner	<p>National and international legal frameworks influencing the federation; GDPR, EHDS, ISO27001, NIS2</p> <p>Governance model of the federation and its implications for host organisation</p> <p>Basic principles of a TRE</p> <p>Format: preferably being kept informed by staff, online guide</p>
TRE Operator/TRE Builder/TRE Developer/TRE Support Staff*	<p>TRE fundamentals; what and why</p> <p>Information security, Security best practices</p> <p>Encryption, secure transfer protocols and criteria and protocols for data anonymisation and statistical disclosure control</p> <p>TRE architecture; zones and functionality</p> <p>Minimal requirements and compliance</p> <p>Federation integration and operating procedures</p> <p>Standards for interoperability</p> <p>Legal requirements for cross-border data sharing</p> <p>Format: online guide, short videos or asciinema</p>

Updated role	Training needs
Policy/Compliance Officer	<p>Legal requirements for cross-border data sharing: National and international legal frameworks influencing the federation, such as data protection laws</p> <p>Regulatory and accreditation frameworks; GDPR, EHDS, ISO27001, NIS2</p> <p>TRE fundamentals to understand the system</p> <p>Format: online reference to legal documents, certified training programs (e.g. for Data protection officers)</p>
Federation Operator	<p>Legal requirements for cross-border data sharing</p> <p>Federation common technical service platform</p> <p>Federation integration and operating procedures; Querying, AAI, interoperability standards</p> <p>Cybersecurity, especially network security</p> <p>Regulatory and accreditation frameworks; EHDS, GDPR, ISO27001, NIS2</p> <p>Format: online reference to legal documents, online training for federation access and linkage</p>
Data Holder / Data Controller	<p>Legal requirements for cross-border data sharing: National and international legal frameworks influencing the federation, such as data protection laws</p> <p>Data security policies, including encryption, secure transfer protocols, measures for data anonymization/pseudonymization and watermarking, in case of data leaks</p> <p>How to upload data to TREs and how to work within TREs</p> <p>Format: online reference to legal documents, online TRE guide or videos</p>

Updated role	Training needs
Data User / TRE User	<p>TRE user fundamentals: access, navigation, import/export, software request, restrictions, statistical disclosure control</p> <p>National and international legislations governing the use and sharing of data</p> <p>Responsibilities and limitations connected to data shared with them by others</p> <p>PI responsibilities (legal and ethical): what may happen to the data that they share, potential consequences and sanctions in case of data breaches</p> <p>Format: online guide, videos, in-person training, certification training</p>
Data manager/Data steward	<p>TRE fundamentals</p> <p>TRE user fundamentals; access, navigation, import/export, software request, restrictions, statistical disclosure control/output checking</p> <p>National and international legislations governing the use and sharing of data</p> <p>Information security and how to handle breaches</p> <p>Encryption, secure transfer protocols, and measures for data anonymization</p> <p>Security best practices</p> <p>Secure archiving options</p> <p>Regulatory and accreditation frameworks; GDPR, EHDS, ISO27001, NIS2</p> <p>Format: online reference to legal documents</p>
Data originator/subject	<p>Information on subject rights, how their data is treated, who can access it under which conditions and the added value to society of opting in</p> <p>Format: online guide, community engagement</p>

* TRE Builder/Operator/Developer/Support often overlap and require many of the same training needs. Specific responsibilities are summarised in Table 2. Note that the role 'TRE Support Staff' may differ among TREs, and may overlap with that of Data Stewards in social science TREs.

We quickly realised many existing TRE providers have similar roles but use varying naming conventions, making harmonisation difficult. As many existing TREs were originally built fit-for-purpose, naming conventions in many cases differed across TREs and the regulations. We found it much more useful identifying the functions and tasks a TRE would need to perform and the training required to achieve those functions, rather than focusing on specific role names at this stage in the project. However, first we needed to use the expanded roles and align those role names with other commonly used naming conventions that perform similar functions to ensure consistency and readability across TRE Providers. These roles, along with alternative naming conventions and a brief summary description are detailed in Table 2. This alignment further assisted in the identification of functions and tasks and helped uncover training gaps which were also found in interviews as part of section 4.3.

Table 2. List of roles and alternative naming conventions, mapped to Principal roles used in the Year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

Role	Alternative Name	Principal role in Blueprint	Brief Description
Data User / TRE User	Data Recipient, Data Consumer, Data Analyst, Data User	Data user	Accesses a TRE with the intent to consume, carry out analysis or research the data
Data manager	Data Protection Officer, Data Engineer, Data Protection Manager, Data Steward, User Support Officer	TRE Governance / Data user	Ensures data in a TRE is maintained and processed in a way useful to a data user. Responsible for the secure control and organisation of sensitive research data within a secure environment
TRE/SPE owner	Top Management, Data Host	TRE Governance	Legal owner
TRE Provider	Data Host, TRE Operator, TRE Builder, TRE Developer, TRE Support Staff	TRE Governance	Processes data on behalf of the controller, (tasks broken down below)
TRE Operator	Data Processor	TRE Governance	Processes data on behalf of the controller, runs the technical day-to-day operations of the TRE. Provides risk and security assessment

Role	Alternative Name	Principal role in Blueprint	Brief Description
TRE Architect	Data Processor	TRE Governance	Carries out the infrastructure development of the TRE
TRE Developer	Data Processor	TRE Governance	Responsible for applications and software infrastructure of the TRE.
TRE Support Staff*	Data Processor	TRE Governance	Provides support functions for the TRE. May include user support, database administrator, quality manager, output checker, auditor, etc.
Policy/ Compliance Officer	Information Governance Manager	TRE Governance	Ensures correct operating policies and procedures for the TRE.
Data Holder/ Data Controller	Data Provider, Data Custodian, Data Access Body, Information Asset Owner	Data holder	Determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, liability, data inclusion, handling incidental finding
Data Originator / Data Subject	Data Provider**	Data holder	Lay person - patient or citizen
Federation Operator	Federation Service Operator, TRE Administrator	Federation Governance	Responsible for the technical services that connect TREs to form a federation.

*These functions are largely carried out by Data Stewards in social science TREs.

** Data Provider is also considered a Data Controller in some contexts, different from a data originator or data subject.

The year 2 version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint (EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3) aligns with the user journey to identify only four principal roles (data user, TRE governance, data holder and federation governance). To move towards consistency and uniformity across the deliverables and work packages, we then sorted the expanded roles that were created after relating to relevant frameworks and conducting interviews to fit under one of the four principal roles. This mapping is provided in column 3 in Table 2 above. Finally, this exercise contributed to the development of the online training guide detailed in section 4.4, and provides consistency of role names with this document, the D14.3 working document, and the user journey.

4.2 Structuring and reviewing existing training material

In this task, we continued to collect, review and categorise training material relevant to handling sensitive data and TREs. The material was shared by EOSC-ENTRUST project members from across all WPs, and includes documents from EOSC, ELIXIR, national initiatives such as HDR-UK, Findata, CSC, SURF and others.

From this collection, we mapped existing resources against the EOSC-ENTRUST roles/Personas and Blueprint components, to help identify training gaps as presented in section 4.3 below and also integrated suitable material into the draft online guide presented in section 4.4.

We found that nearly all existing training material focuses on researchers and TRE users (Blueprint: Data users) and not on TRE Providers (Blueprint: TRE Governance). Federation Governance is not targeted at all within this material at this stage. There is some material on legal and governance topics, such as a GDPR webinar by ELIXIR and the EHDS Community of Practice, but this is fragmented and not (yet) tailored to TREs. Table 3 highlights existing material that can be useful for building a TRE and/or onboarding personnel to a TRE, and also the relevant Blueprint components.

Table 3. List of existing material that could be useful for building a TRE and/or onboarding personnel to a TRE. Extracted from the full list provided in Appendix 1.

No*	Title	Blueprint component	Comments
9	TSD Whitepaper	Architecture specifications, Operating procedures	Describes system setup for a TRE. Good for operators and TRE architects.
16	Data Spaces Support Centre	Architecture specifications, Interface definitions	Covers federation services and glossary useful for TRE operators.
17	FEGA onboarding guide	Legal agreements, Architecture specifications	Clear model for how to onboard a federation.
20	EGI TRE Landscape report	Architecture specifications, interoperability	Defines functional components and technical requirements. Good for new TREs.
23	Norwegian SPE minimum requirements	Architecture specifications, Legal agreements	Defines national SPE minimum requirement to meet EHDS

No*	Title	Blueprint component	Comments
27	EOSC-ENTRUST D17.1 Training material for the use of AAI for TREs pilot implementation**	Interface definitions	Describes all AAI interfaces for the EOSC-ENTRUST federation
32	Network for safe data access professionals (SDAP)	Architecture specifications	Defines competencies but not training; good template for training material.
37	TRE Greenpaper, UK 5 SAFEs	Architecture specifications	Good policy-level reference for builders and owners.

* Related to number in the full list in Appendix 1

**Draft report, not yet published

4.3 Mapping training needs and gaps among TRE Provider Personas

To identify the most relevant topics of the Training package - enabling organisations to build and operate interoperable TREs capable of joining the EOSC-ENTRUST federation, we analysed the key factors currently hindering TRE Providers from adopting the components and standards indicated in the Year 1 version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture (EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4). We reviewed the gap analyses published by the TRE Providers (EOSC-ENTRUST D10.1) and Driver projects (EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1, EOSC-ENTRUST M8) when attempting to validate and adopt the year 1 Blueprint. We further interviewed four existing TRE Providers (Bianca/UPPMAX, Sweden, de.NBI Cloud, Germany, SURF/SANE, Netherlands, and CSC, Finland) and one emerging TRE Provider (GRNET, Greece) to map 1) the level of existing procedures and material for onboarding and training their personnel and material and 2) their impressions of the additional training that would be necessary for them to be able to adopt the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Architecture.

The TRE Provider gap analysis highlights a lack of standardised training for TRE operators, gaps in TRE federation readiness and a fragmented understanding of compliance across the different EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Providers. At this point, no common standard or baseline is defining a TRE architecture and also a varying operational status of the TREs. Further, the legal and regulatory frameworks are confusing, and their interpretations vary across countries and TREs. The EOSC-ENTRUST federation services and interfaces are still largely undefined, as is the governance model of the TRE network, although the emerging year 2 Blueprint architecture is improving this situation. The D7.1 and M8 Driver reports (EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1), (EOSC-ENTRUST M8) also revealed domain-specific training gaps, especially around audit disclosure control and the user journey.

The TRE Provider interviews (summarised in Table 4, minutes available for project members (EOSC-ENTRUST Interviews) confirm the impression from the Provider report (EOSC-ENTRUST D10.1), and indicate a strong need to move beyond user-centric “safe researcher” training toward a structured, role-specific, and federation-ready onboarding curriculum for TRE operators and governance actors. The interviews showed that TRE personnel rely heavily on ad-hoc, internal onboarding (e.g., SOPs, wikis, mouth-to-mouth transfer) and that they have no federation-specific training yet available. Very little openly available material seems to target TRE Provider Personas, a view that is further supported by the review of existing relevant training material presented in section 4.2 above.

Table 4. Examples of training across five EOSC-ENTRUST TREs

TRE	Status	Training strengths	Training gaps	Training mode
Bianca, Sweden	Secure cluster based on UPPMAX HPC	Mature researcher support	Federation-specific training Legal-ethical cross-border guidance	Internal documentation Self-paced tutorials and videos
GRNET, Greece	Emerging TRE	Technical IAM* competence Mature HPC environment	Federation-specific training, cross-TRE interoperability and alignment	Internal documentation for onboarding, intro tutorials and ad-hoc training
de.NBI Cloud, Germany	Operates several TREs for life science and bioinformatics	Well-defined user onboarding and SOPs	Federated AAI, API security and governance alignment	Mainly technical documentation
SANE, Netherlands	TRE built on top of SURF Research Cloud	Advanced IAM (SRAM, eduGAIN), automation, SOPs, ISO frameworks	Federation-specific awareness - cross-TRE data access, legal context, needs training material for operators and auditors	Internal wiki, on-the-job training

TRE	Status	Training strengths	Training gaps	Training mode
CSC, Finland	National sensitive data services	Automation, strong MFA, modular architecture, compliance with Secondary Use Act	Federation interoperability, data transfer standards, audit chain, operator awareness of EU-wide frameworks	Minimal manual onboarding, strong documentation, missing joint federation material

*Identity and Access Management

Cross-cutting findings across all sources (list of existing material, EOSC-ENTRUST deliverables and TRE Provider interviews) suggest that:

- Federation readiness remains the largest unmet need
- Operator training on TRE interoperability (AAAI, APIs) is almost entirely absent, although training material on AAAI is being developed in another EOSC-ENTRUST WP
- Training on legal frameworks is inconsistent and fragmented
- The level of automation and documentation is high among several TREs, but has not been turned into reusable learning sources
- Safe researcher training is strong across TREs, and this could serve as a model for TRE Provider training

Addressing any of these issues would greatly support TRE Providers in becoming federation-ready. These issues have therefore guided the development of the initial draft training modules in section 4.4 below.

It is important to emphasise that personnel across TRE Providers still harbour considerable competence on such topics, but that very little seems to be openly available, documented and formalised, and hence little is available for reuse for new TRE providers. Also, since the level of federation among European TREs is very low, very little of this competence has been set into practice in a TRE setting.

4.4 Draft online guide for getting “federation ready”

The overarching objectives of the EOSC-ENTRUST project is to create a European network of TREs for sensitive data and driver interoperability by developing a common Blueprint for federated data access and analysis. The initiative addresses the current fragmentation in sensitive data research, which “suffers from attendant frictions and bottlenecks in data

sharing and is a significant drag on research productivity” (DARE UK). Building on the training gaps identified in sections 4.2 and 4.3, we have drafted an online guide (EOSC-ENTRUST Guide) as a modular open-access handbook, for the time being aimed primarily at TRE Providers, or the collective EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint role TRE Governance, preparing to join the EOSC-ENTRUST federation. It is being prototyped on Read-the-docs / GitHub pages, allowing version control, cross-referencing and future community contributions.

The online guide’s rationale is threefold:

- 1. Standardisation and trustworthiness**

The general view is that trustworthiness is derived largely “from standardised, centralised processes and systems, where feasible” (DARE UK). The online guide aims to provide the educational foundation necessary for TRE providers to implement and conform to these common standards, facilitating transition to consensus-based topics and Standard Operating Procedures.

- 2. Addressing training gaps**

The guide addresses the main training and knowledge gaps needed for technical and governance compliance. It focuses on three key areas:

- a. Federation Readiness
- b. Legal and Ethical Harmonisation, and
- c. Operational Alignment

- 3. Facilitating EOSC integration**

The guide supports participating TREs in meeting the requirements to become compliant EOSC Nodes. It facilitates their integration into the broader EOSC Federation, which represents a pan-European network of interconnected services designed to enable secure, efficient, and collaborative research across institutional and national boundaries.

The content of the guide mirrors the structure of the ENTRUST Blueprint, and is divided into modules corresponding to the five core components of the ENTRUST Blueprint:

1. Architecture Specifications
2. Template Legal Agreements
3. Operating Procedures
4. Interface Definitions
5. Glossary

The technical requirements in the guide specify that TREs are expected to operate Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) (EOSC-ENTRUST D17.1) compliant with the AARC Blueprint Architecture (BPA) (AARC), connecting to a

centralised federation service as relying parties, ensuring consistent trust and identity management across the network.

The following topics seem to meet the largest training gaps and will be prioritised in the further development of the online guide:

1. Federation readiness
 - a. Enabling federated AAAI in TREs, with cross-TRE authorisation (aligned with training material in preparation from EOSC-ENTRUST Technologies WP (EOSC-ENTRUST D17.1))
 - b. Secure data transfer, audit trails
 - c. Federation governance
2. Legal and ethical harmonisation
 - a. Alignment between national and international legislations
 - b. EHDS permits, secondary use, roles
3. Operational alignment
 - a. Guides to EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture components, understand the minimal requirements and how to comply
 - b. Go from informal, ad hoc operator training to consensus-based topics and SOPs
 - c. Risk management alignment

The online guide will eventually mirror the structure of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture to ensure consistency between technical specifications and training content.

5. Discussion and conclusions

In the Year 1 version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package, we raised the challenge of developing training material to accompany the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint architecture in tandem with the components of this Blueprint being defined and developed. During Year 2, the Training package has evolved into a structured, role-based curriculum that is better aligned with the emerging Blueprint architecture. The iterative work with TRE Providers, Drivers, and the Blueprint architecture itself has provided a clearer understanding of both the technical and governance realities that TREs will meet when they are preparing for federation.

The updated mapping of roles and functions has highlighted training needs in operational TREs and ensures that the learning objectives are directly relevant to building, operating, and governing interoperable TREs. The online guide initiated during this reporting period mirrors this and provides a live resource that can evolve alongside the Blueprint architecture specifications.

European TREs are still at the very starting point when it comes to federation. Infrastructures are mature nationally but lack shared technical and legal frameworks for cross-border interoperability. It is therefore not surprising that training materials on federation services, federated AAAI, and interoperability standards are almost entirely missing across Europe. EOSC-ENTRUST is addressing this gap, but it will take time before training can be fully aligned with stable federation interfaces.

In parallel, the interviews and reports (D10.1, D7.1, M8) reveal that local TRE maturity and scope vary widely, leading to diverging expectations about federation readiness. Some TREs demonstrate mature internal documentation and automation, but lack reusable training content. Others are at early stages of establishing TRE services, but have internal material that can be repurposed. The modular training provided by the online training guide will allow TREs to adopt and adapt training components as they develop.

Legal and regulatory topics seem to be challenging for many of the roles addressed by EOSC-ENTRUST. GDPR awareness is widespread, but understanding of EHDS and the implications of its implementation is still inconsistent.

Another recurrent gap concerns the translation of technical procedures into formalised learning. Most TREs possess high internal competence, but knowledge transfer relies on internal wikis, informal mentoring, or ad-hoc onboarding. By structuring these through the online guide, we can transform local expertise into federated capacity-building resources.

Finally, sustainability and adoption of the Training package is still unresolved, a challenge that we see across all deliverables of this project. For this to have long-term value, it should be integrated with existing structures that ensure maintenance also beyond the project lifetime, such as the EOSC Federation, ideally paired with the final EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider catalogue (EOSC-ENTRUST D14.2) and the Open Provider Forum, which is currently being established in WP11, the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Forum.

5.1 Conclusion

To conclude, the year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST Training package has brought us further towards a shared European understanding of how to make TREs federation-ready. By connecting operational roles, legal responsibilities, and Blueprint components through a coherent training framework, the deliverable helps turn fragmented material into actionable capacity building.

The main outcomes of the year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST Training package are as follows:

- Consolidated and harmonised role-based training needs aligned to the four principal roles of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint: Data user, TRE governance, Data holder and Federation governance
- A mapping of existing training resources and identification of significant gaps, particularly in federation services, AAI, and legal harmonisation.
- A draft online training guide structured according to the five Blueprint components.

6. Next steps

The year 2 version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package has established the conceptual and structural foundations for supporting the building and operation of federation-ready TREs. During year 3 of the project, we will shift from consolidation and mapping toward implementation, validation and sustainability. The next phase will ultimately lead to the final collection of training materials for building interoperable TRE services, according to the final version of the Blueprint, after which funding for continued development is uncertain. The final year will therefore focus on developing new learning material to fill the identified gaps, validating the online guide with TRE Providers, and not least ensuring that the training resources become a sustainable and integral part of the EOSC-ENTRUST framework.

In detail, the next steps will include:

1. **Development of targeted training modules**, addressing all relevant roles, aligned with the components of the Blueprint: architecture specifications, legal frameworks, operating procedures and interface definitions. We intend for these modules to:
 - a. provide step-by-step guidance for TREs to achieve federation readiness, particularly on AAI implementation and cross-TRE data transfer.
 - b. expand coverage of legal frameworks, focusing on EHDS and GDPR compliance and alignment between national and EU legislations
 - c. convert existing internal documentation and SOPs into reusable training material, openly available through the online guide
2. **Validation of training material** by TRE Providers and Drivers, to ensure that the training modules indeed have practical relevance. This should include:
 - a. Pilot selected modules with TRE Providers and collect structured feedback
 - b. Test usability of the guide during onboarding of an emerging TRE (if any)
 - c. Repeat interview series with additional TRE Providers
3. **Expansion of audience and scope** beyond TRE Providers, which were the focus of the current deliverable, to gradually understand the training needs of Data holders and Federation operators as well.

4. **Ensuring long-term sustainability** and integration of the Training package, by defining a maintenance and governance model for curation and update of the online guide after the end of EOSC-ENTRUST

As in years 1 and 2, continued development of the Training package will need to take the following challenges into account:

- Federation interfaces and governance models are still being defined; training can only be scoped to the level that specifications exist.
- Terminology and role definitions continue to evolve as the Blueprint matures.
- Variability in TRE maturity makes common training design complex.
- Limited reusable open training content exists for operators and federation actors.
- The sustainability and ownership of the online guide post-project remain to be defined.

7. Impact

In the Year 1 version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Training package, we described the personas that will interact with the EOSC-ENTRUST network and their training needs. In the year 2 version we further aligned these needs to the Year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. In this phase, we also examined existing training materials from TREs and SPEs that are potential participants in the federation. Linking the training package directly to the Blueprint helps the providers to translate abstract architectural specifications into concrete actions, and may act as a bridge between the high-level planning and operational implementation.

This mapping exercise with the TREs/SPEs has revealed critical gaps between the existing training material and what is needed to fulfil the minimal requirements for joining the federation. Addressing these gaps will increase the federation's readiness, ensuring that the providers can operate within a harmonised framework. In addition, it may lead to increased sharing of experiences, raising common challenges and to co-developing improvements to the training itself, eventually promoting a common understanding of legal and ethical responsibilities, and strengthening legal and data governance across institutions.

By promoting common standards, shared resources and co-development of content, the training package can contribute to higher consistency and quality across TREs/SPEs. It is also important to remember that this training package will be a living document, thus improving as the Providers get more experienced with the federation. A shared, standardised training framework will reduce the fragmentation of TRE operations,

strengthen trust across the federation, and accelerate the adoption of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint across Europe.

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9. Appendix

9.1 Revised list of existing training material on TREs

Live updated list available to project partners from EOSC-ENTRUST project shared folder (EOSC-ENTRUST List)

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
1	TeSS collection - RDMbites: Sensitive data	RDMKit	Data user, TRE governance	Operations	Yes	Short video presentations: Introduction for users, governance for data sharing agreements. Basics of data sharing and how to write data sharing agreements
2	How to perform federated analysis of human cohort data	EBI	Data user	Information	No	Introduction for users, basic steps to follow from finding data to computing and making results available
3	Developing canonical 'safe researcher' training materials for trusted research environments	GESIS	Data user, Data holder	Legal	No	Paper describing process of identifying necessary training, training material available online
4	ELIXIR Webinar: Requirements in data protection law and the upcoming General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) implementation	ELIXIR	All	Legal/ governance Webinar is focused on GDPR.	No	Dated. Presentation from 2018

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
5	EHDS Community of Practice	EHDS	All, especially TRE Governance	Governance /legal and Architecture	Maybe	Focus on health data, mostly governance, does have a video on Architecture
6	EOSC Nordic Training Hub	EOSC-Nordic	All	Information	No	Training library consisting mostly of presentations of information on project deliverables and FAIR. A bit dated as the deliverables represent EOSC from 3-4 years ago. Does provide some suggestions that could be useful to TRE Providers, but I do not consider it training.
7	2 min explainer on Using Patient Data for Research - What is a Secure Data Environment/ Trusted Research Environment?		All	Information	No	Information for general public
8	HUNT Cloud onboarding material and curriculum	HUNT Cloud, NTNU	TRE Governance			
9	TSD White paper	UiO IT division	TRE Governance	Operations and Architecture - System description	Yes	Not a training module, but does provide a TRE system description
10	SAFE White paper	UiB IT division	TRE Governance			

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
11	CSC user guide for sensitive data services	CSC	Data user	Comprehensive guide and using sensitive data services offered by CSC	Yes	Most is focused towards the user but there is valuable information for TRE providers
12	CSC Definition of Sensitive Data	CSC	Data user	Information	No	General information on using sensitive data meant for users
13	CREATE TRE Onboarding Process for Trusted Research Environment (TRE) by Kings College London	Kings College London	Data user, TRE Governance	Architecture and Governance	Maybe	Purpose is for users but does get into ingress/egress processes allowing TRE providers to understand some of the architecture. Guide for using the TRE, but also provides architecture and security information, addressing some governance.
14	UK Office for National Statistics's Safe Researcher Training	ONS	Data user	User training	No	Mandatory required safe researcher training. Online training with a test for researchers. All seems to be focused on the researcher.
15	SAIL Databank Safe Researcher Training	SAIL Databank	Data user	User training	No	Mandatory. Online training with a test for researchers.

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
16	Data spaces support centre	Data spaces support centre	All	Operations and Architecture	Yes	A lot of information, not necessarily focused on TREs. Good glossary, quite extensive, but lacks regulatory references. Also technical building blocks and information on federation services could be useful for TRE Providers.
17	FEGA onboarding guide	FEGA	All	Governance	Yes	Good overall information at all levels, including legal and governance. I think a good training model structure to follow for our website.
18	RDMKit on the Norwegian tool assembly for sensitive data	RDMKit	All	Information	Yes	Overview of TSD. Mostly information, although detailed and well presented
19	HDR UK Futures learning platform	HDR	All		Maybe	Need to register for training. Unsure what the training consists of. No course list or access without registration. I am not sure we want a registration based service?

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
20	EGI TRE Landscape report	EGI	TRE Governance	Operations and Architecture	Yes	Paper, includes list of basic functional requirements, components, and some technical requirements. Also discusses implementation and interoperability. Good resource although still quite high level. Does provide Technical Requirements for TREs. Actually provides four separate definitions of a TRE. Perhaps their example would be a way to present the various terminology differences used for roles?
21	Versatile Trusted Research Environments : An approach for Switzerland	BioMEDIT	TRE Governance	Information	No	High level paper on what TREs are, some basic capabilities TREs should have. Seems more as a paper used to sway decision makers on the value of TREs
22	TEHDAS2 M7.1 Draft guideline on how to use data in a secure processing environment		Data user	Project deliverable. Includes basics on a TRE, mostly in a FAQ format. Also includes user journey and glossary	Maybe	The glossary names three roles (health data access body, health data holder and health data user)

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
23	Norwegian list of requirements for SPE user organisations, to accommodate EHDS		TRE Governance Data user	Project deliverable draft: recommended minimal requirements for TRE in Norway	Yes	Does provide minimal requirements that must be fulfilled to be a SPE. Also provides limited definitions. However, it is nation specific.
24	User guide for Findata's Kapseli users	Findata	Data user	Technology specific	Maybe	How to use Kapseli guide. It provides information on one specific technology, but some information could be generalized to use towards requirements or training.
25	User instructions Statistics Finland's Fiona	Statistics Finland	Data user	Technology specific	No	Seems specific to FIONA and user focused.
26	SANE documentation from SURE	SURF Research Cloud	Data user, TRE Governance	Training	Yes	Course material for users to access as well as data providers to provide their data. Quite extensive wiki. They view the data provider as a co-TRE provider and the training reflects that. A bit different structure than the TREs in Norway

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
27	EOSC-ENTRUST D17.1 Training material for the use of AAAI for TREs pilot implementation	EOSC-ENT RUST	TRE Governance	Internal ENTRUST documents.	Yes	Basic introductory information on how to properly use the EOSC-ENTRUST Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting Infrastructure (AAAI) in its piloting phase.
28	HDR UK safe people registry, standardising how we determine whether researchers are "safe", which will require standardised training	HDR-UK	Data user, TRE Governance		No	Basic info on TREs. Offers training, but as internships/apprenticeships, etc.
29	Competency framework for Research Technical Professionals that are involved in the design and creation of secure data environments	Supporting Research Technical Professionals Project	TRE Governance		No	Says it is a collaboration to develop and support research technical professionals into SDEs. Not available online, must take contact for info.
30	UK data service capacity building	UKRI	Data user	Project.	No	No outcomes yet, check back later.

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
31	Survey on data curation skills for sensitive data from a project coordinated by HDR UK	HDR-UK	Data holder, TRE Governance		No	Track results when done. Cannot access. No longer active
32	Network for Safe Data Access Professionals (SDAP)	SDAP	TRE Governance Data user	Architecture	Maybe	SDAP Competency Framework identifies competency areas that a TRE operator should know at different stages of their career. Useful reference, but does not provide training in these competencies. SDC handbook details what type of information needs to remain safe and how to use outputs. Provides some basic powerpoint slides as training but specifically omits training on Safe Settings.
33	SANE Training Hands-On Session Instructions.pdf	SURF Research Cloud	TRE Governance Data user	Information	No	Project lifecycle: requesting a project, roles, responsibilities, role assignment, analysis steps, and output checking. Was presented as a hands-on training for users or data providers
34	TEHDAS2 public consultation on implementation of SPEs	TEHDAS2	TRE Governance	Guidelines	yes	Draft minimal requirements for SPEs under EHDS

#	Description of training material	Author	Target Personas	Structure	Relevant for TRE Providers	Comments
35	Technical specification for Health Data Access Bodies on the national metadata catalogue	TEHDAS2	Data holder	EU Deliverable	Maybe	As a stand-alone deliverable, it would be difficult to use for training. It should be reviewed again once it is complimented by other deliverables from the project.
36	UK TRE Glossary	DARE-UK (?)	All	Governance	Yes	Glossary that provides references
37	Trusted Research Environments (TRE) Green paper	UK Health Data Research Alliance	All	Information	Yes	Gives an overview of the 5(6) SAFEs in UK
38	The ASSURED project	Trusted Research Environments from Germany and the UK	Data users, Data stewards	Moodle training modules	No	Developing training for data users and data stewards/support staff. Materials not available online, but happy to give access to the Moodle modules if that helps. The team are also happy to collaborate in training development.
39	myDRE	The Dutch Digital Research Environment anDREa	Data users	Information	No	e-learning course on using anDREa
40	Dutch National Statistics Office TRE	Dutch National Statistics Office	Data users	Information	No	Guide for users to conduct their own research on microdata